

TYPOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The heightened interest in the comparative study of languages among Soviet linguists is explained by the increased role of the Russian language in our multinational country and throughout the world, the process of bringing nations and nationalities closer together, and the desire to improve the teaching and learning of foreign languages. languages, the inclusion in the curriculum of universities that train teachers in foreign languages of a discipline called “comparative typology of native and foreign languages”, the introduction of the principle of referring to the facts of the native language when developing methods for teaching a non-native language.*

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For the pedagogical process of teaching a foreign language, the identification of typologically important structural differences between a foreign language and the students' native language, with which they constantly compare the foreign language they are learning and from which they constantly build, is of primary importance.

Language, the most important and amazingly perfect means of human communication, a means of exchanging thoughts, can perform these diverse and complex functions because it is a very flexible and at the same time.

This type of typological research, that is, comparative. Typology of native and foreign languages is one of the sections of the private typology. Comparative study of languages has not only practical, but also theoretical significance. It makes it possible to determine the general linguistic status of linguistic units, to study more deeply the structure of each of the languages being compared, and to determine trends in linguistic processes. It also helps to identify those features of native and non-native languages that remain out of sight when they are studied separately.

Comparative learning of languages is carried out at all levels and sublevels of the language hierarchy, including at the lexical level, in particular at its sublevel of word composition.

Comparative study of linguistic units and especially lexical units in various languages has a certain significance for the development of the general theory and practice of translation, including for the methods of teaching lexicology and methods of teaching foreign languages. at the same time a perfectly organized system. Like any system, language has two sides. It consists, on the one hand, of elements - phonemes, morphemes, words, clothed in the material substance of sound, and on the other hand, it has structure. The structure of a language should be understood as its internal organization, the pattern of connections and relationships of the countless number of its elements, named above and ensuring its functioning in the form of an act of communication.

We are adding words after I.V. Arnold is understood as “a combination of two or, less often, three bases, functioning as one whole and standing out in the composition of a sentence as a special lexical unit due to its integrity” [1. P. 150]. “Word composition reflects the specifics of the language, since, along with some features common to many languages, it has national features characteristic of a given language, constituting one of the differences between one language and another” [2. P. 68].

Each language is linguistically unique relative to all other languages. On the one hand, it is also true that “this originality is a relative phenomenon: its content is determined by the language with which the given language is compared. What is specific in language A when compared with language B may turn out to be non-specific in comparison with language C” [3. P. 50]. On the other hand, a comparison of the system of unrelated languages, in particular the English composition with the system of composition in the Uzbek language, contains more striking, large distinctive features of the English and Uzbek composition.

Thus, we can make the task easier by comparing the phenomena of interest to us within unrelated languages. In this case, we will receive a fairly informative description of the distinctive features of English composition from Uzbek. However, comparison within related, especially closely related, languages shows us a picture of distinctive details, subtleties, etc., since the main essential features in this case obviously coincide.

There is not enough information in the linguistic literature about what is meant by national specific composition of words. This issue is most fully covered in the book by E.A. Vasilevskaya “Verbal composition in the Russian language”, where there is a special chapter - “National originality of word composition”. The author of this book outlines the following parameters for describing the specifics of compounding: 1) the presence or absence of compounding as such in the language; 2) intensity, specific gravity, prevalence of complex words in the language; 3) types of complex words functioning in the language; 4) correspondence of phrases in one language to complex words in another; 5) the ability to denote certain concepts with complex words or phrases; 6) the relationship between additions and fusions in the lexico-grammatical structure; 7) presence or absence of a connecting vowel; 8) the arrangement of components, the order in which they follow each other within a complex word [4. P. 78]. Even a cursory glance at this list suggests that some of the criteria for comparison are of a general nature, that is, applicable to any or almost any pairs of languages being compared, while other criteria are applicable only to certain pairs.

Of course, an important parameter is the inventory of models, identifying the stems of which parts of speech can be combined with the result in the form of a complex word. E. Sapir speaks about this, in particular: “Some languages allow the composition of all or nearly all types of elements. Paiute, for instance, may compound noun with noun, adjective with noun, verb adverb with verb, verb with verb. Yana, an Indian language of California, can freely compound noun with noun and verb with noun, but not verb with verb. On the other hand Iroquois can compound only noun with verb, never noun and noun as in English or verb and verb as in so many other languages” [9. P. 67].

An interesting criterion is “the arrangement of components, the order in which they follow each other within a complex word.” Applying this criterion to identify the national specifics of word composition, B. Ismailova compares words of the same meaning in a pair of languages and discovers that in English compound words the arrangement of components is reversed compared to Kyrgyz, which emphasizes the difference between these languages in the field of word

composition. On the other hand, commonality is found for English and Kyrgyz languages. Of course, similarities or divergences in this regard can only be revealed by comparing a large number of words [5. P. 35]. collocation national language.

The national flavor of such nouns in the Uzbek language as *otsotsol*, *olapes* is determined by national customs, beliefs, prejudices, and traditions. Among the Uzbeks, a thick beard has always been considered a sign of nobility, and a person with a white beard received the name *otsotsol* in the Uzbek language, which is not typical for the English language. This word is translated into English as a whole phrase, and man with white beard and moustache is an old man with a gray beard and mustache. A difficult word, the appearance of which is associated with national prejudice: *olapes*. In countries with subtropical and sharply continental climates, some people develop white spots on their skin. It was generally accepted that these people were “unclean.” Thus, a complex noun appeared in the Uzbek language, characterizing a person with his appearance - *olapes*, a direct equivalent to which we will not find in English.

Nouns used to describe a person's appearance and character are a word with one or more stems. Nouns used to describe a person's appearance may include simple nouns in English, and complex nouns in Uzbek: blond - *mallasoch* - "blonde", "blonde"; brunette - *tsorasoch* - “brunette”, “brunette”.

It should be noted that nouns with a simple stem used to describe a person's appearance create an image of the person as a whole, while nouns with a complex stem evaluate the appearance of the person being described, highlighting a conspicuous attribute of appearance. This phenomenon can be seen in both languages. For example, sunny-faced girl, well-built youth. Her steel-gray eyes go through you and see granite-hewn features (Christie, p. 157). His loosely-slung muscular arms were all ideal for the game (Doyle, p. 58).

The vocabulary of the language, its most changeable and mobile side, is constantly replenished with new words. Some words are replaced by others, words completely unrelated to others before become synonymous with each other due to the emergence of new meanings in them. Words that were previously common and necessary become less common and gradually turn into archaisms or completely fall out of linguistic use, etc. The level of development of a language is determined not only by the richness of the number of words in its vocabulary, but also by the richness of words and means that more clearly express various semantic and stylistic shades.

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Languages, the inclusion in the curriculum of universities that train teachers in foreign languages of a discipline called “comparative typology of native and foreign languages”, the introduction of the principle of referring to the facts of the native language when developing methods for teaching a non-native language.

As A. Khadzhiev rightly pointed out, the same terminological disagreement is also characteristic of the system of *redushka* words in modern Uzbek and other Turkic languages. For example, the Uzbek scientific literature on reduplication contains terms like: *kusha ouz*, *zhuft suz*, *takrorii suz*, etc[3].

Some linguists use these terms without differentiating meaning and function, while others differentiate them. For example, following Gotsdy, B.A. Makarenko⁴ identifies complete doubling

(duplication) and incomplete doubling (reduplication) as means of word formation, and repetitions, which act as syntactic means and are not related to the formation of new words. This division is primarily based on the study of reduplication in word-formation and stylistic aspects. As for the grammatical use of this phenomenon, it is not considered at all. It is not taken into account that along with affixation, internal inflection, additions, function words, word order and many others, reduplication can be used as grammatical means in conveying one or another grammatical meaning.

In the modern Uzbek language, the process of reduplication has reached a high degree of productivity. Such a wide distribution of re-spirited words is undoubtedly of great interest when studying the structural and semantic features of this type of word and its formation.

It should be noted that reduplication in the Uzbek language, taking into account its semantic, formal and functional features and in connection with its vocabulary, grammar and stylistics, has not been studied. It was considered when studying paired words (i.e. words with reduplication) in general. We find the available materials either in sections of various monographs, manuals, articles, or in special studies devoted to paired words. Among the latest works, we can mention the candidate's dissertation and manual by Y. Abdurakhmanov.

Many issues of reduplication in various categories of words were also considered in the works of A. Gulyamov, where there is an attempt to classify methods of reduplication words, as well as some types of derived reduplication words.

Certain structural and semantic characteristics of paired words are discussed in the grammar of A.N. Kononov, in the academic publication of the Uzbek language, etc.

There are, of course, some works that provide comparative examples from different languages, either historically or non-historically synchronic. However, it can be said that this phenomenon has not yet been sufficiently studied in linguistics.

In addition, there are a number of problems that are characteristic of the system of each of the languages being compared. They can be briefly presented as follows: a/ independent existence of components of reduplicative words, i.e. semantic motivation of components; b/ morphemic nature of the components; c/ morphonological characteristics of sound structure; d/ quantitative limitation of repeating components; d/ questions of phonetic symbolism and many others. From the point of view of universality, the isomorphic and allomorphic nature of the presence and absence of certain features of reduplicative words is important: a/ definition of semantic universals; b/ determination of the nature of expressiveness; c/ determination of structural isomorphy and allomorphy and establishment of their general parameters.

It is interesting to note that at one time G. Marchand made a peculiar attempt to compare the degree of alternating vowels in English and Turkish. At the same time, he argues that English reduplicative words are characterized by the alternation of a vowel of a higher rise with a vowel of a lower rise, while the opposite phenomenon is characteristic of the Turkish language.

The urgent need for practical mastery of a foreign language, primarily English, which is taught in national audiences in schools and universities of our republic, puts forward, first of all, the task of directly addressing the native Tatar language of students and truly relying on it.

The intensive development of comparative research in recent decades is, of course, associated with the enormous interest in foreign languages caused by information needs and the development of scientific and technological progress. The Republic of Tatarstan increases its international status and authority every year, its international contacts expand and strengthen.

Therefore, it is relevant and timely to develop the foundations for the comparative study of foreign and native languages at all levels: from grammar to vocabulary and phonology.

The essence of the comparative typological study of languages, without which, by the way, modern linguistic research is unthinkable, is to identify the most characteristic similarities and differences in the linguistic structure of the languages being compared. Based on the analysis of languages with different structures, a general theory of word formation should be created. For a comparison of languages of various types helps to determine the characteristics of each of them, their classification and systematization, the determination of the most significant differences in linguistic structures in general and at their individual levels, as well as the establishment of common features for languages, leading to the identification and description of linguistic universals.

In terms of the practical significance of this kind of research, it is assumed to identify and solve specific problems leading to specific results: a) application of the identified systemic features of the studied and native languages in the practice of teaching a foreign language, as well as in the theory and practice of translation; b) comprehension, development and research of the basic principles of comparison of systems of differently structured languages (English and Tatar) and theoretically based methods of teaching a foreign language in a national audience; c) development and implementation of optimal recommendations for practical mastery of the foreign language being studied.

The semantic-syntactic characteristics of the adverb in the verb group based on the material of the German and Tatar languages were undertaken in the works of V.M. Romanova and F.S. Shakirova (1978). By analyzing the word order “determiner + qualifier” and the types of syntactic connections, as well as the semantic-syntactic characteristics of the members of the verb group, the authors try to give us the opportunity to see the typological specificity of the German and Tatar languages.

The study of monographic and dissertation research, analysis of scientific and theoretical literature allows us to conclude that the theory of word formation and a comparative description of the word formation of parts of speech and their interaction are in a state of progressive development and improvement. At the same time, the problem of parts of speech, the principles and patterns of their classification, the search and identification of their differential features, as well as issues of interaction and interconnection of linguistic entities continue to be the subject of heated debate and careful study. There is also no unanimity regarding the norms of coincidence of structural-semantic features of words in certain classes; the problems of interchangeability of constituents in certain operating conditions have not been sufficiently studied. The ambiguity of the solution to the above issues, the lack of a comprehensive study of the adverb and its interaction in languages of different structures in terms of comparative typological analysis determined the choice of the research topic.

In modern linguistics, more and more attention is paid to problems that reflect the general trends in the evolution of language and its lexical composition. The direct connection of language with extra linguistic factors represents an opportunity for scientific research. “The reason for the emergence of new words and new meanings of old words for the most part lies in changes in social life, in the development of production and other areas of human activity, as well as the development of thinking”. The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that in English and Uzbek lexicology, complex verbs are less studied than complex adjectives and complex nouns, although

they are quite actively involved in the speech act. While studying a foreign language, students encounter some difficulties in rethinking them, since many translation and explanatory dictionaries lack very common compound verbs.

That is why, in our scientific work, we decided to compare the mechanism of formation of complex words, the structure and semantics of complex verbs in English and Uzbek languages, to analyze and identify both common and distinctive properties that exist in these two, both genetic and really unrelated languages.

All languages have word formation, but methods or types of word formation may have varying degrees of occurrence in languages, i.e. For languages of one type, affixation is more characteristic, for another - composition, for a third - conversion, etc. The above indicates that the systems of all specific languages of the world need a typological inventory of the word-formation system. However, the goals and purposes of a typological inventory may be different. The maximum task of a technologist in this regard is to study word-formation means to determine the types of linguistic structure and to establish word-formation universals. The minimum or narrow task of a typologist is to fix the basic word-formation means in systems of quantitatively limited languages, establish interlingual correspondence, etc., which is a necessary step for preparing answers to typological questionnaires, which are necessary for a uniform description of languages and the creation of universal grammars.

The solution to such questions undoubtedly enriches our knowledge about the general problems of linguistics, for, according to individual linguists, “general linguistics does not yet know its subject: linguists may know, to one degree or another, what takes place in a particular language, but they do not know properly what can take place in the totality of languages. Indeed, we know something about languages, but how much do we know about the language itself - about what can and cannot be in it, what phenomena in it is connected with what is natural and what is accidental, etc.” [3]. The above data indicates that global problems of linguistic description and generalization of language facts can be carried out by studying the systems of specific languages in terms of comparison, by drawing up specific punch cards according to the structure of which of the languages being compared.

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